

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 6: Study 3

Participant Information Sheet

Title of study: Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Study 3: Training evaluation.

Thank you for your interest in taking part in this study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important that you understand why this research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. You may discuss it with others if needed.

Please contact us if you have any questions or need further information. Our contact details are further down the page.

This content is adapted with permission from [participant information sheet and consent form templates](#) developed by the Research Governance, Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.

Quick summary

- This study is being organised by researchers from OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH).
- We are aiming to identify the outreach, marketing, and communications activities that open science advocates take part in; the barriers they experience regarding these activities; and their needs and preferences regarding training in these topics. We would also like to assess whether training affects open science advocates' knowledge and confidence about core concepts in outreach activities. Finally, we would like to receive feedback about the OSPARK Bootcamp training programme.
- As part of this study, you will be asked to take part in two questionnaires: one before you begin the OSPARK Bootcamp, and one after you complete it.
- Your data will be stored on the survey platform and will be accessible only to the [OLS](#) and [DRA](#) teams until data analysis begins. Anonymised data will be shared on an openly accessible GitHub and/or Zenodo repository. All data storage will be in compliance with UK data protection legislation.
- This study is part of the Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp, funded by the first OSCARS Open Call. The OSCARS project has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to understand how open science advocates engage in outreach activities, and what barriers prevent them from doing so. It also aims to identify what training open science advocates feel they need in marketing, communications, and outreach activities. We would also like to compare how knowledgeable and confident open science advocates are about core concepts in outreach activities before and after they take part in the OSPARK Bootcamp training programme. Finally, we would like to collect participants' feedback about the OPSPARK Bootcamp.

Who can take part?

Anyone attending an OSPARK Bootcamp is eligible to take part in this study. We hope to recruit approximately 30 participants.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study will involve completing two questionnaires—one before starting the OSPARK Bootcamp training programme, and another upon completing it. Each questionnaire will involve:

1. Giving informed consent;
2. Answering knowledge-based questions about outreach, marketing, and communications;
3. Giving some information about your confidence conducting outreach activities;
4. Providing some demographic information;
5. Closing message.

Additionally, in the first questionnaire, you will be asked about your existing outreach activities, the barriers to conducting such activities that you have experienced, and your preferences for training formats. In the second questionnaire, you will be asked for feedback about the OSPARK Bootcamp.

We expect that each questionnaire will take approximately 15 minutes.

What will happen to my data?

This research will be conducted in compliance with data protection legislation. Your data will be stored and managed by OLS (Open Life Science Limited), a UK based social enterprise. As part of this study, we will be collecting questionnaire responses with a pseudonymous code to allow linking the two questionnaires. No directly identifiable data (such as IP addresses) will be collected. Your registration for the OSPARK Bootcamp is

stored separately to your questionnaire responses and is managed by the DRA (Digital Research Academy GmbH), a Germany based company.

This study has been designed according to open science principles. Anonymised data will therefore be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY\)](#) license, unless deemed to be a risk to participant safety or wellbeing.

Our full data management plan [<add link when available>](#) is publicly accessible.

What are the possible benefits, risks, or disadvantages of taking part?

The benefit of taking part in this study is having the opportunity to shape training on outreach, marketing, and communications for open science initiatives.

There is a risk that your responses may be identifiable, despite anonymity, as there are some open text boxes and open science is a relatively small field. To mitigate this, the researchers will check open text responses and anonymise any potentially identifiable information.

What if something goes wrong?

If you would like to withdraw from the study, you can do so any time by closing the questionnaire tab. Incomplete and unpaired responses will be deleted from the dataset prior to analysis.

If you have any concerns about any aspects of the study, you should contact the lead researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

Should you remain unhappy with the response and wish to make a formal complaint, please make a report under OLS's [Code of Conduct policy](#).

What will happen to the results of the research?

Upon conclusion of this study, the findings may be written into a scientific journal article and presented at scientific conferences. This is to share our results with other researchers in the field. You can get updated about the findings of this research by signing up to the [OSPARK mailing list](#).

The anonymous data from this study will be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons](#)

[Attribution \(CC-BY\) 4.0 International license](#). This means that other researchers may use the data to verify our results or conduct their own research in the future.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is led by a team of researchers at OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH). OLS is a non-profit company limited by guarantee, based in the United Kingdom (company number [12824090](#)). DRA is a grassroots trainer network based in Germany (HRB 295646).

The research team for this study consists of the following people:

- Bethan Iley, OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager, OLS
- Heidi Seibold, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Joyce Kao, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Yo Yehudi, Co-Executive Director, OLS

The development of this survey was also supported by contributions from the following individuals:

- Doaa Abdelkader, The British University in Egypt & Open Science Community Egypt, Egypt.
- Anastasiia Afanaseva, Saarland University, Germany
- José Francisco Pereira Cardoso, Department of Clinical Sciences, University of Lund, Sweden.
- Jens Dierkes, University and City Library Cologne, University of Cologne, Germany.
- Christian Meesters, NHR SouthWest, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Germany.

The development of the overall research project was additionally supported by the following people:

- Deborah Udoh, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Nigeria
- Riva Quiroga, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Chile

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Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by *<name of research ethics committee or IRB>*. If you have any questions or concerns about the ethics review for this study, you can contact them at *<IRB email>* using reference *<reference number>*.

Contact for Further Information

If you have questions or comments about the study, please contact the lead researcher on this study:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

If your questions or concerns remain unresolved, please contact the Principle Investigator:

Yo Yehudi
Executive Director
yo@we-are-ols.org

Thank you for your interest in this study and for taking the time to read through this information page.

By indicating that you consent to taking part in the research on our event sign-up page, you are agreeing to the following statements:

- I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information presented above about this study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and these have been answered fully.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason and without my legal rights being affected.
- I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from Open Life Science Limited and that my personal information will be held and handled in compliance with data protection legislation.
- I understand that data collected as part of this will be accessible to employees and contractors at Open Life Science Limited (also known as OLS) and DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH (also known as DRA). I give permission for these individuals to have access to this information.
- I understand that the information I provide may be published as a report. Anonymity will be maintained and it will not be possible to identify me from any publications.

- I agree that my anonymous survey responses can be deposited in repositories such as GitHub and/or Zenodo to promote transparency and public accessibility to research.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

We will be linking responses to the questionnaires using unique identifiers. Please create your unique identifier using the following:

- Your favourite dessert. If you don't know what your favourite dessert is, please enter your favourite colour, book, movie, etc.
- Your month of birth as a number.
- The first two letters of your mother's first name.

Please put a hyphen (-) between each element of the identifier.

For example: someone whose favourite dessert is tiramisu, who was born in January, and whose mother is called Mary would enter tiramisu-01-ma.

Please enter your code below:
